

A STUDY ON DATA DRIVEN MODEL FOR CITIZEN-CENTRIC GOVERNANCE AMONG VARIOUS RURAL SELF-GOVERNMENTS IN TIRUPATTUR DISTRICT OF TAMIL NADU STATE

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ABSTRACT

Data driven models are effective tool that can make rural self-government as citizen centric governance. This research explores the connection of data-driven models and citizen-centric governance, emphasizing the importance of leveraging data for informed decision-making and responsive service delivery. The study investigated the implementation levels of data-driven models in various rural self-governments (Panchayat Raj Institutions) in Tirupattur district of Tamil Nadu State. The study carried out on the various dimensions of citizen centric governance such as responsiveness, fairness, responsibility, and accountability. The findings reveal a mixed picture, with significant opportunities for improvement in the implementation of data-driven models for citizen-centric governance. The study also found that there is recognition of the transformative potential of data-driven governance in promoting citizen engagement and transparency as well as challenges like limited ICT empowerment and lack of awareness. The study underscores the need for comprehensive data-driven frameworks and policy interventions to bridge these gaps and realize the full potential of citizen-centric governance. By fostering greater data literacy and investing in technology infrastructure, governments can empower rural communities to actively participate in decision-making processes, ultimately leading to the creation of more resilient and inclusive societies.

KEYWORDS: Panchayat Raj Institutions, Citizen-centric governance, Data-driven models, Transparency, Accountability, Responsive governance, Fair governance, Inclusive communities, etc.,

INTRODUCTION

Citizen-centric governance, a fundamental concept in public administration, emphasizes the active engagement of citizens in decision-making processes and the delivery of public services. In citizen-centric governance, citizens are placed at the heart of decision-making processes. It encompasses various mechanisms such as participatory budgeting, citizen advisory boards, and online feedback platforms to actively involve citizens in shaping policies and services. This strategy helps governments better meet the needs and preferences of citizens while also fostering a sense of empowerment and ownership among them (Estevez and Janowski (2013) highlights the transformative potential of citizen-centric governance in enhancing government responsiveness and accountability. Similarly, Hood and Margetts (2007) argue that citizen-centric approaches promote trust in government institutions by creating opportunities for meaningful engagement and dialogue between citizens and policymakers. By leveraging data-driven technologies and innovative communication channels, governments can facilitate greater citizen involvement and transparency, promoting collaborative problem-solving to complex societal challenges and co-production of public

value. Practice of citizen-centric governance will foster more resilient and inclusive communities.

NEED OF THE STUDY

A data-driven model is essential for enhancing citizen-centric governance due to its capacity to improve decision-making processes, promote transparency, and increase government responsiveness. By leveraging the model, governments can gain valuable insights into citizens' needs, preferences, and behaviors, enabling them to tailor policies and services more effectively. Moon and Bretschneider (2016) emphasizes the importance of data-driven decision-making in public administration, highlighting its role in optimizing resource allocation and performance management. Moreover, data-driven approaches facilitate evidence-based policymaking, reducing the reliance on intuition or political considerations and enhancing the overall quality and efficiency of governance interventions (Chen, Chiang, & Storey, 2012). Data-driven models help to track and measure the impact of initiatives in real-time, allowing for continuous feedback with citizens. This iterative process fosters greater accountability and trust in government institutions, as citizens can observe tangible results and provide input on ongoing projects. Adopting a data-driven model is need of the hour for advancing citizen-centric governance by enabling evidence-based decision-making, fostering transparency and accountability, and promoting inclusivity and responsiveness to citizens' needs.

DATA DRIVEN MODEL FOR CITIZEN CENTRIC GOVERNANCE

Data-driven models are a framework which includes various data related to citizen centric governance. It plays a vital role in enhancing efficacy of citizen-centric governance for informed decision-making, policy formulation and delivery of services. These models utilize vast datasets to identify trends, anticipate challenges, and optimize resource allocation for promoting transparency and accountability in governance processes (Howard, 2019). For example, in healthcare, data-driven approaches enable better resource distribution and healthcare planning, ensuring equitable access to services (Alami et al., 2020). Citizen centric governance is constituted by responsive governance, fair governance, responsible governance and accountable governance (Ivanyna, Maksym & Shah, Anwar. 2009).

OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

The study aims to deepen the understanding of how data-driven models can contribute to the advancement of citizen-centric governance and provide insights into practical strategies for harnessing the power of data to improve governance outcomes. Present study was carried out with following objectives.

1. To know the implementation level of data driven model for citizen centric governance
2. To know the implementation level of data driven model for responsive governance
3. To know the implementation level of data driven model for fair governance
4. To know the implementation level of data driven model for responsible governance
5. To know the implementation level of data driven model for accountable governance

METHODOLOGY

The research type adopted for this study was quantitative and descriptive design was employed. The study carried out in Tirupattur district of Tamil Nadu State and covered ten panchayats. 50 elected representatives were identified as samples using simple random sampling technique for the purpose of this study. An interview schedule was developed based on the objectives of the study to collect primary data from the respondents. This schedule encompassed six dimensions and 23 items, utilizing a four-point scale to measure the items. The scale was excellent, good, average and below average. The findings from this study have been discussed on the same four-point scale. This methodological framework ensured the systematic and structured approach to understand the perceptions and experiences of elected representatives on data driven model for citizen centric governance.

MAIN FINDINGS AND DISCUSSION

DATA DRIVEN MODEL AND CITIZEN CENTRIC GOVERNANCE

Data-driven models are instrumental in promoting citizen-centric governance by enabling governments to tailor policies and services to meet the specific needs and preferences of citizens. Through the analysis of data, governments can gain valuable insights into citizen behavior, preferences, and priorities, allowing for the development of targeted interventions and personalized services (Helbig et al., 2012). Moreover, data-driven governance facilitates greater citizen participation and engagement in decision-making processes. By making data accessible and transparent, governments empower citizens to actively contribute to policy discussions, provide feedback, and monitor government performance. This participatory approach ensures that government actions are aligned with the interests and aspirations of the public, thereby fostering a stronger relationship between citizens and government (Linders, 2012). The present study found that more than half (56%) of the respondents articulated that their rural self-government (panchayat) implements the data driven model at below average level. Less than half (44%) of the respondents said that the panchayat implements the data driven model at average level. The reasons behind these facts, may be, panchayats would have not been empowered with ICT knowledge and also may not aware of the need and importance of the citizen centric governance. These blocks can be removed with the support of financial and excusive policy on data driven models by states. Data driven models in governance promotes citizen-centricity by enabling personalized services, enhancing citizen engagement, and strengthening the relationship between citizens and government.

DATA DRIVEN MODEL AND RESPONSIVE GOVERNANCE

Responsive governance is one among the dimensions of citizen centric governance for the purpose of this particular study. This dimension covered things like the provision of public services in accordance with citizen preferences, direct interactive democracy, protection of life, liberty, and property, peace, order, and the rule of law, freedom of speech and choice, improvements in social and economic outcomes, and enhancements in public service accessibility, quantity, and quality (Ivanyna, Maksym & Shah, Anwar. 2009). Data driven governance promotes transparency and accountability by providing insights into policy outcomes and performance metrics. Citizens can actively engage with initiatives of rural self-government, contribute feedback, and hold authorities accountable for their actions. Through data driven platforms, rural self-governments can enhance citizen participation and foster a culture of collaborative performance (Smith, 2017). The study reveals that a little less than half

(48%) of the respondents said that the rural self-government implements the data driven model at below average level while more than half (52%) of the respondents expressed that their rural self-government implements the data driven model at average level to respond the needs of their citizen. Whenever a need arises, ad-hoc kind of data collection took place and decisions were made based on those collected data. The collected data may not be wholistic, therefore there could a possibility for deserving citizen to miss the service of rural self-government. Hence, a comprehensive data driven model is required in addressing similar types of needs among the citizen. Integration of such data-driven models in governance will facilitate responsive decision-making, enhances transparency, and fosters citizen engagement.

DATA DRIVEN MODEL AND FAIR GOVERNANCE

Fair governance measured with the items such as fulfillment of citizens' values and expectations in relation to participation, social justice, and due process; access of the poor, minorities and disadvantaged groups to basic public services; non-discriminatory laws and enforcement; egalitarian income distribution; and equal opportunity for all (Ivanyna, Maksym & Shah, Anwar. 2009). Data driven models plays a crucial role in promoting fair and equitable decision-making processes. By analyzing the data, rural self-government can identify and mitigate biases, and ensuring that policies and interventions are implemented in a manner that upholds principles of fairness and justice. Data-driven models enable policymakers to assess the impact of their decisions on various demographic groups, thereby reducing disparities and promoting inclusivity (Osoba & Welser IV, 2017). Through data driven models or initiatives, rural self-governments can provide citizens with access to information about policy decisions, resource allocations, and outcomes. This transparency empowers citizens to hold authorities accountable for their actions and advocate for policies that address the needs of all members of society. By incorporating data-driven approaches into governance frameworks, rural self-governments can enhance trust and confidence in public institutions, thereby strengthening the social contract between citizens and the state (Hendler et al., 2012). The study reveals that a little more than three fifth (61%) of the respondents said that the rural self-government implements the data driven model at below average level and more than one third (39%) of the respondents expressed that their rural self-government implements the data driven model at average level to practice fair governance. Integration of data-driven models in governance fosters fair decision-making, promotes transparency, and enhances accountability, ultimately contributing to a more equitable and just society.

DATA DRIVEN MODEL AND RESPONSIBLE GOVERNANCE

Data driven models are instrumental in fostering responsible governance by enabling evidence-based decision-making and promoting efficient resource management. For the purposes of this study, responsible governance entails competitive service delivery, winning confidence, managing risks, operating more efficiently and effectively, maintaining the integrity of its operations, and putting results first. It also comprises open, transparent, and sensible economic, fiscal, and financial management. (Ivanyna, Maksym & Shah, Anwar. 2009). By leveraging data driven model, rural self-government can gain insights into societal needs, anticipate emerging challenges, and formulate policies that are responsible to the needs of citizens (Goldsmith & Eggers, 2004). The study discloses that two third (67%) of the respondents said that the rural self-government implements the data driven model at below average level and a little less than one third (33%) of the respondents expressed that their rural self-government implements the data driven model at average level for being responsible governance to their citizen.

DATA DRIVEN MODEL AND ACCOUNTABLE GOVERNANCE

Access to justice and information, judicial independence and integrity, effective oversight by the legislature and civil society, the ability to recall officials and rescind programs, effective restrictions for government intervention, and effective barriers against special interest capture are all aspects of accountable governance (Ivanyna, Maksym & Shah, Anwar. 2009). Data-driven models play a pivotal role in fostering accountable governance by providing mechanisms for transparency, oversight, and evaluation of rural self-government actions. Data driven approach enables stakeholders to hold rural self-government entities accountable for their decisions and actions by providing clear evidence of performance and outcomes (Janssen et al., 2012). Furthermore, data-driven governance promotes accountability by enhancing public participation and engagement in decision-making processes. The study confirms that two third (46%) of the respondents said that the rural self-government implements the data driven model at below average level and a little less than one third (54%) of the respondents expressed that their rural self-government implements the data driven model at average level for being accountable governance to their citizen. By making data driven model accessible through open platforms and interactive tools, rural self-government empowers citizens to actively contribute to policy discussions, provide feedback, and monitor government performance. This increased transparency and citizen engagement foster a culture of accountability wherein rural self-government officials are held accountable not only by internal mechanisms but also by the public they serve (Moon, 2002).

CONCLUSION

In the realm of governance, the integration of data-driven models holds immense promise for advancing citizen-centric principles. This study underscores the pivotal role of data-driven approaches in enhancing governance efficacy across various dimensions. Findings reveal that while there is progress in implementing data-driven models, there remains significant room for improvement, particularly in rural self-governance contexts. The study emphasizes the transformative potential of data-driven governance in promoting citizen engagement, transparency, and accountability. Through the analysis of data, governments can better understand citizen needs, preferences, and behaviors, leading to more targeted and personalized service delivery. However, the research also highlights existing gaps, such as limited ICT empowerment among rural self-governments and inadequate awareness of citizen-centric governance principles. Addressing these challenges requires concerted efforts, including financial support and policy interventions to promote the adoption of data-driven models. By enhancing data literacy and investing in technology infrastructure, governments can empower rural communities to participate more actively in decision-making processes. Overall, the findings underscore the need for comprehensive data-driven frameworks to realize the full potential of citizen-centric governance. By leveraging data-driven approaches, rural self-governments can foster more inclusive, responsive, and accountable governance systems, ultimately leading to the creation of resilient and thriving communities.

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REFERENCES

1. Alami, H., Gagnon, M. P., & Fortin, J. P. (2020). Somei wat grey: areas of opacity in the understanding of the concept of big data governance in the context of health technology assessment. *International Journal of Technology Assessment in Health Care*, 36(1), 1-6.
2. Chen, H., Chiang, R. H., & Storey, V. C. (2012). Business intelligence and analytics: From big data to big impact. *MIS Quarterly*, 36(4), 1165-1188.
3. Estevez, E., & Janowski, T. (2013). Electronic government for sustainable development: Conceptual framework and research agenda. *Government Information Quarterly*, 30(4), 1-10.
4. Goldsmith, S., & Eggers, W. D. (2004). *Governing by network: The new shape of the public sector*. Brookings Institution Press.
5. Helbig, N., Gil-Garcia, J. R., & Ferro, E. (2012). Understanding the complexity of electronic government: Implications from the digital divide literature. *Government Information Quarterly*, 29(3), 497-506.
6. Hendler, J., Berners-Lee, T., & Schindler, R. (2012). Web science: an interdisciplinary approach to understanding the Web. *Communications of the ACM*, 55(10), 33-37.
7. Hood, C., & Margetts, H. (2007). *The tools of government in the digital age*. Palgrave Macmillan.
8. Howard, P. N. (2019). The data-driven governance of digital technology, big data, and the Internet: New roles and responsibilities for state and society. *Third World Quarterly*, 40(2), 265-285.
9. Ivanyna, Maksym & Shah, Anwar. (2009). Citizen-Centric Governance Indicators: Measuring and Monitoring Governance by Listening to the People and Not the Interest Groups. *Bavarian Graduate Program in Economics (BGPE), Working Papers*. 10.2139/ssrn.1726727.
10. Janssen, M., Charalabidis, Y., & Zuiderwijk, A. (2012). Benefits, adoption barriers and myths of open data and open government. *Information Systems Management*, 29(4), 258-268.
11. Linders, D. (2012). From e-government to we-government: Defining a typology for citizen coproduction in the age of social media. *Government Information Quarterly*, 29(4), 446-454.
12. Moon, M. J. (2002). The evolution of e-government among municipalities: Rhetoric or reality? *Public Administration Review*, 62(4), 424-433.
13. Moon, M. J., & Bretschneider, S. (2016). Government performance management in the United States: From data to reporting. *Public Performance & Management Review*, 39(1), 7-31.
14. Osoba, O. A., & Welser IV, W. (2017). *An intelligence in our image: The risks of bias and errors in artificial intelligence*. Rand Corporation.
15. Smith, M. A. (2017). Open data and responsive governance: Lessons from the Open Government Partnership. *Social Science Quarterly*, 98(2), 548-562.